

Accelerated EPG-based myocardial T1 mapping with PENGUIN

Catarina N Carvalho^{1,2*}, Andreia S Gaspar², Rita G Nunes², Teresa M Correia^{1,3}

¹Center of Marine Sciences (CCMAR), Faro, Portugal; ²Institute for Systems and Robotics - Lisboa and Department of Bioengineering, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Lisbon, Portugal; ³School of Biomedical Engineering and Imaging Sciences, King's College London, London, United Kingdom

*catarina.neves.carvalho@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

Abstract

INTRODUCTION: Model-based Deep Learning (DL) allows accelerating MRI reconstruction and quantitative mapping. Here, we propose a DL architecture that performs myocardial T1 mapping directly from accelerated k-space, which models the signal with the Extended Phase Graph (EPG) formulation, to allow more accurate quantification. The DL architecture is a modification of Phase Graph signal and Gradients QUantitative Inference machiNe (PENGUIN)¹, with the following novelties: (a) quantitative mapping is performed directly from undersampled k-space; (b) signal intensity curves are simulated not only for a range of T1 values, but also for a range of regular heart rate (HR) values.

METHODS: PENGUIN (Figure 1a) combines a Recurrent Inference Machine² with a dictionary of EPG simulated signal evolution curves that provides the network with a pre-calculated signal model. PENGUIN performs $J=2$ inference steps to obtain J estimates of the T1 maps, considering the L1-norm loss function evaluated in the myocardium. Networks were trained for acceleration factors $acc=\{4,8\}$, ADAM optimizer, learning rate= $1e-4$, for 300 epochs, $C=64$ and $C=256$ channels for acceleration factors 4 and 8, respectively. Data were obtained from MICCAI's 2023 CMR reconstruction challenge³. T1 mapping was conducted following a 4-(1)-3-(1)-2 MOLLI sequence, short axis (SA) view only, FOV= 360×307 mm², spatial resolution= 1.4×1.4 mm², slice thickness= 5.0 mm, TR= 2.67 ms, TE= 1.13 ms, partial Fourier= $7/8$, and GRAPPA factor of 2, on a 3T MAGNETOM Vida Siemens scanner. K-space data were undersampled retrospectively, following a radial k-t sampling trajectory with golden angle increments. EPG-based simulations were implemented for HR= $[28,102]$ bpm, T1= $0:1:2000$ ms, T2= 50 ms. Ground-truth T1 maps were obtained by performing a pattern recognition approach over the reconstructed, fully sampled signal intensity images, through dot product matching. Zero-filled (ZF) and Compressed Sensing (CS) reconstructions were performed to compare with PENGUIN.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION: PENGUIN's T1 maps (Figure 1b-c) achieved mean relative errors of $10.1\pm 11.0\%$ and $15.9\pm 15.4\%$, and mean MSSIM scores of 0.999 ± 0.001 and 0.998 ± 0.001 , for $acc=4$ and 8 , respectively. PENGUIN is less resource-consuming than CS reconstruction, since the computational burden is moved to the preprocessing stage.

Figure 1 – (a) PENGUIN architecture for inference step j . The estimate p_j is given to the dictionary to obtain the signal-intensity and corresponding derivative of each T1 value in p_j . The gradient of the negative log-likelihood ΔL_j is calculated, concatenated to p_j and given as input to the network, which outputs the incremental update to the estimated maps. h_j : memory vectors. (b) T1 maps of 5 distinct test subjects (rows), $acc=4$; ground truth (GT), Exponential Fitting, zero-filled (ZF), compressed sensing (CS), and PENGUIN. (c) T1 relative errors and MSSIM scores obtained for all testing images; * (p-value <0.05) and *** (p-value <0.001).

References

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